

No Hilbert Einstein Action With Positive Dark Energy / Cosmological Constant From A String Action

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Abstract:

The paper revisits our past analysis of the ability of superstrings to model vacua with positive cosmological constant/dark energy effects. We explicitly call out the impossibility for superstrings to recover the Hilbert Einstein action, or de Sitter (stable, metastable or unstable) vacua with positive cosmological constant, or time-varying effects.

1. Introduction

This paper calls out a result from [181], revisiting and expanding the reason of [14,15].

In [14] we provided a reasoning that shows that the string action à la Nambu-Goto, or Polyakov [182-184], contains the Hilbert Einstein action. It also shows that dealing with positive or negative cosmological constant requires different reasonings.

As a result it is plausible that one of these cases be in the string swampland (See [15] and references therein). Said otherwise, superstrings can't model vacua with positive cosmological constant. Then, we then argue that this result extend to dark energy effects, which may be time-varying. We also discuss how it applies to attempts at creating stable, unstable or metastable de Sitter vacua, e.g., with quintessence [190].

Finally, we show that the absence of flat spacetime encountered in [6,162,177,181], was already inherent to [14,15]. Both approaches are consistent.

2. The Original Analysis From Curvatures

In [14], with figure 1 reproduced here, we show that with the definition of the Ricci scalar, the different expression of superstring actions systematically contain the Hilbert Einstein action: extremizing the former extremizes the latter.

The difference between treating negative curvature extremization (directly matching the string action sign) vs. positive curvature (requiring mathematical handling with sign change and/or shift as mentioned in [14]) hints that,

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while GR and gravitons² are recoverable and contained in the string actions, strings may not be able to similarly handle or generate negative and positive curved spacetimes, and that may impact QFT vacua (spacetime without matter, i.e. at minima excitation).

This analysis is valid for any spacetime dimension D .

Figure 1 – The Ricci Curvature scalar is computed as a limit of ratio of deficit surface of small spheres [185]. The Nambu-Goto or Polyakov actions extremization operations extremize an area which is, to the first order, equivalent to extremizing grand circle surfaces for a D dimensional Hilbert Einstein action (with a sign difference and up to a monotonic transformation). String action invariance under Weyl metric transformations, ensures covering other “inclinations of the grand circles” in one shot. A Einstein Hilbert action would instead also consider smaller circles and multiple effects and it would also consider non-conformal cases (where different inclinations are not equivalent). However, as explained in the text, in the presence of strings, we would expect that the background or derived fields will be “essentially” conformant also (as an effective model of the impact of the strings). Therefore, the extremization of string actions, computed over the whole manifold of spacetime, contains and is essentially equivalent to, at least to the first order, the extremization of the Hilbert-Einstein action, computed over the whole manifold of spacetime. However we need to “play” with the sign: the string action is always positive (area), but equivalently (through a monotonic transformation) decreasing as curvature increases while the Ricci curvature scalar can be positive or negative. Yet extremizing one amounts to extremizing the other, by changing the sign (and adequately shifting to ensure all encountered Ricci curvature scalars are of the same sign when extremizing if we wanted to match the same action appearance): the string action (in a covariant volume) increases (as the manifold is uncompressed and so the area contribution of (σ, τ) can increase), as the Ricci curvature over an covariant volume decreases (negatively), i.e. the manifold is uncompressed) and conversely. This analysis was hinted in [1], but not detailed. (Figure and Caption are from [14]).

² However, note that, based on the multi-modal work, gravitons are unphysical (at best quasi particles living outside spacetime, in AdS(5)(+5...)).

Section 4.2 in [15] shows that the reasoning above spacetime generated by a string action à la Nambu-Goto, or Polyakov [182-184], correspond always to a negative cosmological constant.

If we consider a localized region in spacetime, if small enough, even a time varying dark energy effect will appear constant. Per variational calculus, as it is at the level of the integrand, repeating the change of variable of [15], the contribution like cosmological “constant” effect only if negative-like, i.e., with a negative potential. Indeed [14,15] operates using the background spacetime curvature. This is why in [181], we can argue that this reasoning applies also to unstable or metastable vacua, including quintessence [15,190]. A positive-like cosmological constant effect, even if time varying can't be generated by background superstrings.

3. Time-varying Dark Energy case

3.1 Lambda not Constant

Locally, in spacetime, the same applies even if time-varying.

Yes [15] showed the possibility to construct positive potential vacua, typically by adding fields. However none of these can be generated by superstrings per the above. On that basis we provide a stronger argument here that these models are not compatible with superstrings, beyond the arguments and problems with these models discussed in section 3 in [15]. In addition in [14] we show different treatments between positive and negative curvatures, in order to have the string action extremize the Hilbert Einstein action. In that analysis, if the curvature is spatially global, even if time-varying, it is really what is to be associated to the background³ superstring spacetime⁴. So when this positive curvature, in [14], it requires an ersatz that cannot ensure that the signs match in the reasoning of [14]. Matter, black holes prevent bounding this, except where black holes are regular, or, in general, when gravity and cosmology have no singularity [1,8-10,22,27,89,131,137,151,152,157,162,177], as in for example multi-fold universe (but there we know that the cosmological constant must be strictly positive), prevent the scheme when the curvature is positive: superstrings cannot produce a asymptotic de Sitter spacetime or vacua. That it be stable, unstable or metastable.

Let us detail this analysis in section 3.2.

3.2 Negative Cosmological Constant + Positive Potential / Field?

3.2.1 Our Curvature Effects-based Reasoning So Far

It is important to notice that throughout [14,15], and the paper so far, we have argued that the string actions can't recover the Hilbert Einstein action as the basis for stating that superstrings can't generate a (background)

³ Because we talk of curvature, it can be a cosmological constant, if not time varying, or a time varying dark energy effect otherwise, proving our point.

⁴ And to some extent the base, i.e., the correct one from the point of view of the relative entropy information measure, metric $g^{\mu\nu}$ field/distribution in [178] and references therein.

spacetime with a positive cosmological constant (or overall global curvature), or associated possible time-varying dark energy effects.

We did so for multiple reasons. Firstly because through our work so far, we have equated cosmological constant and its microscopic interpretation of effects like multi-fold dark energy effects, fractal, non-commutativity, discreteness, etc., as discussed in [1,6,8-10,16,23,27,29,32,36,53,59,62,68,72,112,131,137,142,148,150,152,155,161,169,170,174-177,179,181], allow us to treat the dark energy effects as a sum of contributions:

$$DE_{\text{Effects}} = \Lambda(x^\mu) = \sum_i \lambda_i (x^\mu) \quad (1)$$

Which says that it is a sum of these microscopic effects (λ_i) mentioned earlier. These may or may not be homogeneous or constant. So far, we may them independent of special locations x^μ for $\mu = 1$ to 3 , but explained, and encountered e.g. in [16,53], that they may depend on $x^0 = t$.

So the conventional Λ , the one in the Einstein equations and the Hilbert Einstein action, is DE_{Effects} , not one of the λ_i .

Reasonings like [14,15], as well as [13], and [112,170,181] are relying on (1), because they operate against the curvature of the background spacetime.

3.2.2 Negative Cosmological Constant + Positive Potential Effects Approach

On the other hand Typically, the way that superstring theorist try to keep superstring relevant, ignoring that supersymmetry is not physical, and, so far, has never observed as in [1,8-10,13,22,112,131,137,152,170,191,200] and references therein), is to suggest that a negative cosmological constant (now a λ_i term) Is complemented by terms like quintessence, leading to (stable), unstable or metastable vacua in a universe generated by superstrings. This is especially common when using Friedman equation.

Consider a spatially flat Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) universe. The expansion dynamics are governed by the Friedmann equations [192-194]. The first Friedmann equation is:

$$H^2 = \frac{8}{3}\pi G(\rho_m + \rho_r + \rho_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}} + \rho_x) = \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where H is the Hubble parameter, G is the gravitational constant, ρ_m is the energy density of matter, ρ_r is the energy density of radiation. The dark energy sector consists of two components:

- $\rho_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}}$: The energy density due to a constant negative cosmological constant, Λ_{neg} . This is given by $\rho_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}} = \Lambda_{\text{neg}} c^2 / (8\pi G)$, (3)

which is a negative constant. Its corresponding pressure is

$$P_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}} = -\rho_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}} = |\rho_{\Lambda_{\text{neg}}}|. \quad (4)$$

- $\rho_x(z)$: The energy density of an additional, possibly dynamical, dark energy component, which evolves with redshift z (or scale factor

$$a = 1/(1+z). \quad (5)$$

Its pressure is

$$P_x(z) = w_x(z)\rho_x(z), \quad (6)$$

where $w_x(z)$ is its equation of state parameter.

The second Friedmann equation, describing the acceleration of the universe, can be written as:

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho_m + 3P_m + \rho_r + 3P_r + \rho_{\text{DEff}} + 3P_{\text{DEff}}) \quad (7)$$

For non-relativistic matter,

$$P_m \approx 0, \quad (8)$$

and for radiation,

$$P_r = \rho_r/3. \quad (9)$$

The effective total dark energy density, $\rho_{\text{DEff}}(z)$, and pressure, $P_{\text{DEff}}(z)$, are:

$$\rho_{\text{DEff}}(z) = \rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + \rho_X(z) \quad (10)$$

$$P_{\text{DEff}}(z) = P_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + P_X(z) = -\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + w_X(z) \rho_X(z) \quad (11)$$

Note that here, DEff is not DEEffects as the models are different, with Λneg is a λ_i .

The effective equation of state for the total dark energy is then:

$$w_{\text{eff}}(z) = P_{\text{DEff}}(z) / \rho_{\text{DEff}}(z) = (-\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + w_X(z) \rho_X(z)) / (\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + \rho_X(z)) \quad (12)$$

For the universe to be accelerating at the present epoch ($z=0$), driven by this effective dark energy, two conditions must be met:

- The net effective dark energy density must be positive:

$$\rho_{\text{DEff}}(0) > 0, \quad (13)$$

which implies

$$\rho_X(0) > |\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}}|. \quad (14)$$

- The effective equation of state must satisfy

$$w_{\text{eff}}(0) < -1/3. \quad (15)$$

This translates to

$$P_{\text{DEff}}(0) < -\rho_{\text{DEff}}(0) / 3. \quad (16)$$

This way, the introduction of a "natural" Λneg from string theory considerations, as in references [15] and [195], might seem appealing.

The observed effective cosmological constant today, $\rho_{\Lambda\text{obs}}$, is extremely small and positive: approximately,

$$\rho_{\Lambda\text{obs}} \approx 10^{-123} M_{Pl}^4. \quad (17)$$

If $|\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}}|$ is of a more "natural" (presumably larger) scale, then $\rho_X(z_0)$ must evolve to a value such that

$$\rho_X(z_0) \approx |\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}}| + \rho_{\Lambda\text{obs}}. \quad (18)$$

This implies a very precise near-cancellation between $\rho_X(z_0)$ and $\rho_{\Lambda\text{neg}}$ to yield the tiny observed positive residual. This does not eliminate the fine-tuning problem but rather shifts its origin to the properties and evolution of the ρ_X component, or to the initial conditions that lead to such a cancellation. Whether this is a more plausible scenario

than explaining the smallness of a single positive Λ remains an open question, though dynamical mechanisms for ρ_x , such as quintessence tracking behavior ([15] and references therein), could potentially play a role in achieving such a state dynamically.

3.2.3 Back To Our Reasoning

This can be also seen by considering the Lagrangian formulation of GR as in [1,137,199] and references there in :

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{HEAction}} + \mathcal{L}_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Matter}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{HEAction}} + \mathcal{L}_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + \mathcal{L}_X + \mathcal{L}_{\sim\text{SM}} \quad (19)$$

$\mathcal{L}_{\text{HEAction}}$ is the Lagrangian density used in the Hilbert action Einstein action without any cosmological constant or Matter term. $\sim\text{SM}$ indicates the Yang Mills fermions and Bosons, i.e., supersymmetric extensions to the SM. $\mathcal{L}_{\sim\text{SM}}$ is the associated Lagrangian density. Examples are encountered in [13,112], and references there in. It includes particle and their interactions.

Modeling spacetime as vacua, without other particle/matter, we see that \mathcal{L}_X must be included on the background spacetime side, and not on the perturbation (due to matter) side:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{HEAction}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{DEffects}} + \mathcal{L}_{\sim\text{SM}} \quad (20)$$

Indeed, by construction or definition, it is where the $\sim\text{SM}$ lives, particles interacts through Yang Mills interactions, and matter curves spacetime. If we consider that $\sim\text{SM}$ particles are excitations of the vacuum, then clearly we must use (20).

A $\mathcal{L}_{\sim\text{SM-X}}$ interaction term should also be added. However in the assumptions are that there are no interactions between $\sim\text{SM}$ matter and X (other than through gravity).

In a multi-fold universe, the spacetime results from 2D random walks of massless Higgs bosons as spacetime preons and the resulting spacetime matter (re)construction [1,6,8-10,22,62,72,124,131,137,152,170,176,177,181]. The $\mathcal{L}_{\Lambda\text{neg}} + \mathcal{L}_X$ term results from Multi-fold dark energy effects and/or non-commutativity of spacetime [1,8-10,22,27,131,137,152,181]. It is time-varying and can also depend on the distribution of matter.

Reasonings from (2) to (18), and [198], while equivalent, do not allow us to see the incompatibilities argued in [14,15]. That is because in [14,15], spacetime is the background spacetime produced by the superstrings (remember the analogy to the base metric field in [178], mentioned earlier). [14] and references therein also show that the Yang Mills QFTs are also included in the superstring action (albeit supersymmetric; another problem per [1,8-20,22,85,112,131,137,152,170,177,178,181]). If such an (a set of) additional field(s), e.g., quintessence, is (are) uniformly distributed across space (constant or not), then it is (they are) part of the background spacetime, and must therefore be part of the $\text{DE}_{\text{Effects}}$ in (1), vs. particle/matter that appear locally through Matter contribution, as it fundamentally changes the background versus local perturbation due to matter. With the vacua being when all matter is turned off.

[14,15] shows that we can't recover a positive $\Lambda = \text{DE}_{\text{Effects}}$ spacetime, from extremizing the string action and quintessence, or other tricks as discussed in [15,195] do not help, as it is the final $\text{DE}_{\text{Effects}}$ that must be generated, and can't be with superstrings.

In that context, [195] is not to be misunderstood. First of all it relies on supersymmetry breaking, which is not an off ramp, and it remains unphysical per [13,30,112,170]. Furthermore, [195] is an example of generating, e.g. à la KKLT, a de Sitter vacua. It does not mean that its extremization still implies extremizing the Hilbert Einstein action, as we discussed that it works well only when the background spacetime has a negative curvature. We won't get a

GR spacetime when reaching classical scales. We argue that it does not, and what is generated is something else: the tangent AdS(5) ++ space to our spacetime. Furthermore, while it may continue preserve Yang Mills, only supersymmetric SM-like models results, even with supersymmetry breaking, which leads to additional consistency problems [13,30].

3.4. Consequences

Consequences are discussed in [181], and they also reinforce the view that supersymmetry, superstring, supergravity and M-theory are unphysical [1,8-20,22,85,112,131,137,152,170,181]. Indeed the above implies that quintessence or unstable or metastable de Sitter vacua are also not compatible with superstring [15,181].

4. Flat Spacetime

In the discussion above, the null cosmological case is a bit fishy (with α and α^{-1} in section 4.2 of [15]). It is because as discussed in [162,177,181,186-189], we see that last spacetime is not possible with a non-commutative spacetime, except if we accept the model of a primordial BEC [162,177,181,186-189]. The case where $\alpha^{-1} = 0$, is however plausible action-wise, as a limit, based on [14], as spacetime is then essentially \sim commutative per [6,181].

Per [6,181], a GR-related spacetime is non-commutative at some scales. Per [150,170], Quantum physics requires such non-commutativity at the scale of the SM fermions.

5. Conclusions

The paper shows that [14,15] have all the arguments to preclude positive cosmological constant, asymptotic de Sitter spacetime, and stable, metastable or unstable vacua with positive potential, including quintessence, in a spacetime defined or generated by superstrings (background). It reinforces the results of [15]. The paper details

We also recover in the reasoning of [14,15], i.e., analyzing the Hilbert Einstein action, and the super string actions, that flat spacetime is a tricky situation that also can't be generated by superstrings, thereby also pushing away any scenarios à la [17], without a primordial BEC [162,177,181,186-189]. The presence of matter or the multi-fold spacetime reconstructions as in [1,6,137,181], based on 2D random walks of multi-fold preons, i.e., massless Higgs bosons [1,8-10,22,70,72,131,137,152,162,176,177,181], will later always be with a strictly positive cosmological constant, just as shown by other considerations in [112,170,181].

As a result we have strong arguments that supergravity, superstrings and M-theory are unphysical, to add to [1,8-20,22,85,112,131,137,152,170,181], and in particular the fact that our real universe is not supersymmetric and never was [1,112,136,170].

The core of the reasoning built on [14,15] is valid in the conventional real universe, not just in multi-fold universes.

We also encountered in the approach of [14,15] the challenges with a flat spacetime, unless if we have a primordial BEC, as discussed in [6,162,177,181] and references therein. It shows the consistency of the approaches.

In appendix A, we superficially review the multi-fold theory.

Appendix A. A Superficial Overview of the Multi-fold Theory

In a multi-fold universe [1-178,179,181,182], gravity emerges from entanglement through the multi-fold mechanisms. As a result, gravity-like effects appear in between entangled particles [1,24,25], whether they are real or virtual. Long range, massless gravity results from entanglement of massless virtual particles [1,26]. Entanglement of massive virtual particles leads to massive gravity contributions at very small scales [1,27]. It is at the base of the E/G Conjecture [24], and the main characteristics of the multi-fold theory [22]. Multi-folds mechanisms also result in a spacetime that is discrete, with a random walk fractal structure and non-commutative geometry [62], in a range of spatial scales, which is Lorentz invariant and where spacetime nodes and particles can be modeled with microscopic black holes [1,4]. All these recover General Relativity (GR) at large scales, and semi-classical model remain valid till smaller scales than usually expected. Gravity can therefore be added to the Standard Model (SM) resulting into what we define as SM_G : the SM with gravity effects non-negligible at its scales. It can contribute to resolving several open issues with the Standard Model, and the standard cosmological model, without New Physics⁵ other than gravity [1,4-178,179,181,182]. These considerations hint at an even stronger relationship between gravity and the Standard Model, as finally shown in [23]. It leads us to consider that the multi-fold theory gives good insight to conventional Physics, that our real universe may be well modeled as a multi-fold universe [1,4-178,179,181,182], something that we have done in this paper.

Among the multi-fold SM_G discoveries, the apparition of an-always in-flight, and hence non-interacting, right-handed neutrinos, coupled to the Higgs boson, generated by chirality flips by gravity of the massless Weyl fermions, induced by 7D space time matter induction and scattering models, and hidden behind the Higgs boson or field at the entry points and exit points of the multi-folds. Massless Higgs bosons can be modeled as minimal microscopic black holes mark concretized spacetime locations. They can condensate into Dirac Kerr-Newman soliton Qballs to produce massive and charged particles below the energy scales of the multi-fold electroweak symmetry breaking [1,4], and as random walk patterns to realize massless particles at all scales [1,29,36,37], thereby providing a microscopic explanation for a the multi-fold kinematics and dynamics and associated unconstrained Kaluza Klein mechanisms [23,33,34,52,63,64,113,139], Higgs driven inflation [1,27], the electroweak symmetry breaking, the Higgs mechanism, the mass acquisition [139], and the chirality of fermions (and spacetime); all resulting from the multi-fold gravity electroweak symmetry breaking [1,4,17,23,29,32-

⁵ Conventional physicists may argue it is New Physics. We consider that it isn't because no new particles or interactions are introduced. We just add gravity, as we know it should be, and multi-fold mechanism and let conventional Physics unfold with the considerations. It does change conventional results or explanations, usually with same observables, and it does live in a discrete spacetime etc. as a result of conventional analysis of these consequences. We also do not cover stable field effects like Skyrmions [166], that we prefer to see as a collective effect for the theory. Beside the SM particles, there are other collective solutions/solitons in gauge theories, they have behaviors as particles but they are quasi-particles composed of collective effects of a large set of particles. We see them as Qballs or patterns that can appear by multi-fold space time matter induction and scattering, under specific circumstances, nothing more. They are topological solitons and can appear in BEC, as expected with massless Higgs boson condensates [171,172].

34,52,64,66,72,74,124,139,140]. The multi-fold theory has concrete implications on New Physics like supersymmetry, superstrings, M-theory and Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) [1,8-21,66,90,112,134].

Multi-folds are encountered in GR at Planck scales [5,6] and in Quantum Mechanics (QM) if different suitable quantum reference frames (QRFs) are to be equivalent relatively to entangled, coherent or correlated systems [7]. This shows that GR and QM are different facets of something that they cannot well model: multi-folds [1,52,94,104].

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